

Spatial Distribution and Temporal Growth of Rice in Kolhapur District

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Abstract:

Rice is the main kharif crop grown in the district. Kolhapur district is considered as the core district in Maharashtra for cultivation of rice. In fact rice cultivation has spread through this district. Especially in western region due to climatic conditions are profitable to rice cultivation. In this research paper Study on the Spatial Distribution and Temporal Growth of Rice in Kolhapur District, including Productivity, Area and Yield. The main objective of this paper is to study Spatial Distribution and Temporal Growth of Rice in Kolhapur District.

Keywords: Rice cultivation, Productivity, Area, Yield.

Introduction:

Rice is the main kharif crop grown in the district. Kolhapur district is considered as the core district in Maharashtra for cultivation of rice. In fact rice cultivation has spread through this district. Especially in western region are gainful climatic conditions including rainfall, soil and humidity. In this regard the Productivity of rice and Production of rice depend upon physical and economic factors. In this research paper Study on the Spatial Distribution and Temporal Growth of Rice in Kolhapur District, including Productivity, Area and Yield in 2018. The main objective of this paper is to study Spatial Distribution and Temporal Growth of Rice in Kolhapur District.

Objectives:

1. To Study on the Spatial Distribution and Temporal Growth of Rice in Kolhapur District.

2. To suggest measures for improvement if necessary.

Research Methodology:

Only secondary data has been collect from Books, Journals, Gazetteer, C-DAP, Kolhapur, Socio-Economic and Statistical Abstract Kolhapur District – 2018. Compressive District Agricultural plan district (C-DAP), Kolhapur. Data of rice productivity is taken 2013 and area under rice cultivation is 2017-2018 for discussion regarding spatial distribution. About the temporal growth of area, production and yield of rice in Kolhapur district data is collected from 2008-2009 to 2013-2014.

Limitation of the study:

The present research is related to specific period and only rice crops in India. The conclusion of this research paper may not be applicable to other crops and other district.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:**Spatial Distribution:****Tahsilwise Rice Productivity Status in Kolhapur District**

Sr. No.	Tahsil	Productivity (2013)
1	Hatkangale	2452.00
2	Shirol	1188.80
3	Panhala	2929.70
4	Shauwadi	2997.80
5	Radhanagri	3323.60
6	G.Bavada	4039.90
7	Karveer	3342.40
8	Kagal	2547.90
9	Gadhingalaj	2143.60
10	Bhudargad	3960.20
11	Ajara	2710.60
12	Chandgad	3410.30
	Total	35046.80

Source: C- DAP, KOLHAPUR.

Table shows that in 2013 productivity of rice is 35046.80 kg/ha. in Kolhapur district. Gagan Bavada tehsil is 4039 kg/ha. these are the highest productivity in the district. After that Bhudargad tahsil was second ranking

(3960.20 kg/ha.) followed by Chandgad, Karveer and Radhanagri tahsils. These five tahsils together share over 50 percent productivity of rice in the district. While productivity of Shirol is 1189 kg/ha. that is the low average in the Kolhapur district.

Tahsilwise Area under Rice Cultivation in Kolhapur District -2017-18.

Sr. No.	Tahsil	Area in ha.	Share in Percent
1	Hatkangale	927	0.84
2	Shirol	80	0.07
3	Panhala	10810	9.80
4	Shauwadi	16170	14.66
5	Radhanagri	13150	11.92
6	G.Bavada	3022	2.74
7	Karveer	11461	10.39
8	Kagal	8786	7.96
9	Gadhingalaj	8386	7.60
10	Bhudargad	13187	11.95
11	Ajara	10575	9.58
12	Chandgad	13782	12.49
	District	110,291	100

Source: Socio-Economic and Statistical Abstract Kolhapur District – 2018.

A) High Concentration Zone: (Above 11,000 ha.):

In table shows that the high proportion of rice cultivation is observed in Shahuwadi, Chandgad, Bhudargad, Radhanagari and Karveer tahsils. This is the core area of rice cultivation with 67,750 ha. in this there are the 61.41 percent of rice cultivated area of the district. These farmers have adopted the rice crop in traditional method also called as 'Rub' method. Availability of suitable climate, well, laterite soil, high rainfall, availability of labours, proper cultivation method and proper planning for cultivation practises are the important contributing factors responsible for the high percent of rice cultivation in this tahsils.

B) Moderate Concentration Zone: (6000 – 11000 h a.):

In the table shows that moderate concentration zone includes Panhala (9.80 percent), Ajara (9.58 percent), Kagal (7.96 percent) and Gadhingalaj (7.60 percent)

tahsils, a second largest rice cultivation tahsils with 38,557 ha. Contributing 34.94 percent of rice area of the district. It is observed that the tahsils well rainfall with good irrigation facility and the famous brand of 'Ajara Ghansal'. Besides these suitable climates, suitability of soil, progressive farmers, availability of local market, availability of transport facilities are the crucial factors contributing for the moderate proportion of rice cultivation in Kolhapur district.

C) Low Concentration Zone: (Below 6000 ha.):

This low concentration zone includes Hatkangale (0.84 percent) and Shirol (0.07 percent) tahsils having 927 and 80 ha. area under rice cultivation respectively. These tahsils share 0.84 and 0.07 percent of rice area respectively to the total area under rice cultivation in the study region. The low rainfall and poor quality black soil has affected rice cultivation in Hatkangale and Shirol tahsils.

Temporal Growth of Rice in Kolhapur District:

Temporal Growth of Area, Production and Yield of Rice in Kolhapur District.

Year	Area 00 ha.	Productivity Kg/ha.	Production 00, MT.
2008-09	1118	2583	2859
2009-10	1071	2569	2763
2010-11	1020	2876	2934
2011-12	971	2641	2564
2012-13	1093	2589	2366
2013-14	1120	3029	2650

Source: Compressive District Agricultural plan district (C-DAP), Kolhapur.

In the table shows that the Rice is the major kharif crop grown in the Kolhapur district. The rice crop grown in 74 percent (112000 ha.) of the total area under cereal crops during the kharif season. Hence, average productivity of the crop is 3029 kg/ha. Ranks 3rd in the state. Table 4.13 and figure 4.5 provide the information regarding the growth of rice area under rice cultivation, production and productivity during the period from 2008-09 to 2013-14.

In 2008-09 area under rice cultivation was 111800 hectare has been decreased by 97100 hectare in 2011-12 because of the cultivation of food grain is shrinking, with cash crops like sugarcane. Beside this its production was 285900 metric tonnes in 2008-09 which decline by 256400 metric tonnes in 2011-12 because of decrease under area of rice cultivation. It has been observed that the productivity was 2583 kg/ha. in 2008-09 which increased up to 2641kg/ha. in 2011-

12 because the farmers grown rice for commercial purpose with high variety seeds. However, in 2013-14 in this year area under rice cultivation again increase that is 112000 hectare and also production which increase up to 265000 metric tonnes. Here notable that the productivity also increased. In this way in 2008-09 to 2013-14 in whole periods here show that area under cultivation which is decreased only accept year 2013-14 and production also decreased accept only year 2010-11. However, here notable that productivity has been increased also.

Conclusion:

Overall discussion on the area, production and productivity of rice in the study region, the researcher conclusions of the study that is the concentration of rice reveals the high concentration in Shahuwadi, Bhudargad, Radhanagari, Chandgad, Karveer, Ajara and Panhala tahsils. Followed by G. Bavada, Kagal and Gadhingalaj tahsils and low concentration is observed in Hatkangale and Shirol tahsils. The temporal variations have also observed trends towards the growth. The average area, productivity and production in rice during the period 2008-2009 to 2013-2014 was 639300 ha, 16287 Kg/ha and 1613600 mt. correspondingly. In this way the Kolhapur district have a good potential for the growth of rice cultivation. If provision of adequate water in the eastern part of the study region made available. Available proper market channels. Government support is important to rice growers e.g. subsidies, grants, easy access to credit, insurance. The government should start rice procurement centres on time and at good prices. The government should encourage farmers to cultivate Gansal rice. More research is needed in rice, mainly including new varieties that are resilient to climate change and resistant to pests and diseases.

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